

A New Species of *Trichodina* Ehrenberg, 1830 (Ciliophora: Trichodinidae) from the Long Whiskers Catfish, *Mystus gulio* (Hamilton, 1822) (Siluriformes: Bagridae) in the Beel Dakatia of Khulna, Bangladesh

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Abstract

During a survey on species diversity of trichodinid ciliates from freshwater fishes in the Beel Dakatia located in Khulna District of Bangladesh, a new species of trichodinid ciliate was identified from the gills of Long Whiskers Catfish, *Mystus gulio*. This ciliate is described here as new species based on distinctness in a combination of morphological characters. The species differs morphologically from its congeners by its relatively small body diameter, with white porcelain Chinese soup spoons-shaped denticle and the argentophobic central area of adhesive disc looks like a centrally located glistening, undivided, almost spotless white circle, surrounded by dark and narrow wrinkle free perimeter and some other measurements.

Introduction

More than 400 species of trichodinid ciliate were described so far from freshwater and marine animals, mostly from freshwater fish species (Wang et al., 2018). They are the causative agents of diseases in the global aquaculture causing, among other things, damage and reduced growth of the host fish (Moraes & Martins, 2004), favouring secondary bacterial infections (Xu et al., 2012) and mortality, all leading to constraints in global aquaculture production (Martins et al., 2015). Many countries have taken initiatives for identifying and discovering appropriate control measures of these ciliates. In Bangladesh, the trichodinid ciliates of freshwater fishes have received considerable attention in recent years. As a result, 45 species of this group representing the genera *Trichodina* Ehrenberg, 1830, *Paratrichodina* Lom, 1963, *Tripartiella* Lom, 1959 and *Trichodinella* Šrámek-Hušek, 1953 were identified from different freshwater and estuarine fishes by Asmat et al. (1997; 2003a,b,c; 2005; 2006; 2017), Bhouyain et al. (1999), Asmat and Sultana (2005), Habib and Asmat (2008), Habib et al. (2010a,b), Kibria et al. (2009; 2010; 2011; 2012), Haque et al. (2018a,b,c) and Kibria and Asmat (2014; 2019). During a survey on species diversity of trichodinid ciliates from freshwater fishes in the Beel Dakatia of Khulna district, Bangladesh, a new species of ciliate was recorded from the gills of a commercially important catfish species of Bangladesh, *Mystus gulio* and described as a new species.

Accepted: 14 December 2019
Published: 22 December 2019

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Figure 1. Map of sampling area from where fishes were collected from the Beel Dakatia in Bangladesh.

Figure 2. Denticle structure and construction of X and Y axes as fixed references for description of denticles (after Van as & Basson, 1989).

Explanations: **AB**, apex of blade; **AM**, anterior margin of blade; **AR**, apophysis of ray; **B**, blade; **BA**, apophysis of blade; **CA**, central area of adhesive disc; **CB**, section connecting blade and central art; **CC**, section connecting central part and ray; **CCP**, central conical part; **CP**, central part of blade; **DC**, deepest point of semilunar curve relative to apex; **DM**, distal margin of blade; **PM**, posterior margin of blade; **PP**, posterior projection; **R**, ray; **SA**, section of central part above x axis; **SB**, section of central part below x axis; **TP**, tangent point; **TR**, tip of ray.

Materials and Methods

Beel Dakatia is one of the large saucers like water bodies of the coastal area of Bangladesh (Rahman et al., 2010). It is located in the southwestern region of the country covering gross area of 11,609 hectare (Rahman, 1995). It lies between longitudes 89°20'E and 89°35'E and latitudes 22°45'N and 23°00'N under the administrative boundaries of Dumuria, Phultala and Daulatpur upazilas of Khulna district (Banglapedia, 2004) (Figure 1).

The host fishes were collected using seine nets and gill nets by local fishermen. Gill scrapings were made at the beel side; air-dried and then transported to the laboratory. The slides with trichodinid ciliates were impregnated with Klein's silver impregnation technique (Klein, 1958) and examined under a research microscope, OSK 9712 T-2 at 10x100 magnifications. Measurements (Figure 2) were made according to the

recommendations of Lom (1958), Wellborn (1967), Arthur and Lom (1984) and Van As and Basson (1989; 1992). All measurements given are in micrometers, range in parentheses by the arithmetic mean and standard deviation. For statistical analysis, morphometric measurements of 20 specimens for both species were considered. Photomicrographs were made in order to have comprehensive morphological analyses of the ciliates. The size of trichodinid is classified following Basson and Van As (1994) as small (less than 35 μm), medium (between 35 and 60 μm) and large (more than 60 μm).

ZooBank registration: ZooBank registration number of the present publication (ICZN 2012, recommendation 8A) is [urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:219DF84E-73DC-4066-9FCA-9A5A22C5658E](https://zoobank.org/pub:219DF84E-73DC-4066-9FCA-9A5A22C5658E). ZooBank registration number of *Trichodina dakatiae* is [urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:6BFF5308-840D4C29-AADF-72D17EA6318E](https://zoobank.org/act:6BFF5308-840D4C29-AADF-72D17EA6318E).

Results & Discussion

Description (n=15): Small-sized ciliate, 21.3-30.1 (27.0 \pm 2.8) in diameter, surrounded by finely striated border membrane, 2.4-2.9 (2.8 \pm 0.2) wide. Adhesive disc concave, 20.4-24.3 (22.2 \pm 1.6) in diameter. Centre of adhesive disc argentophobic, 4.9-5.8 (5.2 \pm 0.4) in diameter, looks like a large central, glistening white undivided circle with a few minute dark granules in and around center (Figure 3A-D). Perimeter of central area narrow, almost round, dark and formed by ray tips. Denticulate ring, 12.6-13.6 (12.9 \pm 0.5) in diameter consisting of 18-21 (19.9 \pm 0.9) denticles. Number of radial pins per denticle 4-6 (4.9 \pm 0.6). Span and length of denticle 6.8-7.8 (7.4 \pm 0.5) and 2.9-3.9 (3.6 \pm 0.5) respectively. Extent of adoral ciliary spiral 380°.

Blade of denticle smoothly curved and broad, and slightly shorter than ray, length 2.4-2.9 (2.8 \pm 0.2). Blade fills more than half space between y and y+1 axes. Distal margin slightly rounded, continuous with anterior margin. Distance between distal margin and border membrane moderate. Tangent point forms line, below of distal margin. Gap between tangent point and following denticle large. Anterior margin forms smooth curve with prominent apex, extending more than halfway towards y+1 axis (Figures 4A-B). Apical concavity present, but not prominent and never impregnated. Anterior and posterior blade apophyses absent. Apex, in most cases, smoothly curved, situated near base of blade, extending middle of y+1 axis. Posterior margin forms moderately curved forming distinct crescent. Deepest point of curve at same level as apex. Interblade space wide, tip of blade never touches anterior margin of next blade.

Central part widely triangular, width 1-1.9 (1.5 \pm 0.5), straight with gradually rounded tip, extending more than half to y+1 axis. Tip tightly

fitted with following counterpart of denticle. Shape of section above and below x axis similar. Indentation in lower central part sometimes distinct.

Ray connection short and broad, and thinner than ray. Ray apophysis, when present, small and anteriorly directed. Ray base thin and same as ray connection. Ray slightly curved in posterior direction, with same width throughout, ray length 1.9-3.9 (3.2 ± 0.7). Ray tip slightly thickened, almost touches or crosses y+1 axis, never touches central clear area. Central groove is not clearly visible. Micro- and macronucleus could not be seen.

Discussion: The presently described species is a small trichodinid and may be characterized for having smoothly curved and broad denticles; blunt tangent point forms line below distal margin; anterior margin forms smooth curve with prominent smoothly curved apex, situated near base of blade; central part widely triangular, straight with gradually rounded tip; ray anteriorly directed but slightly curved in posterior direction, with same width throughout and slightly thickened ray tip; and central area of adhesive disc argentophobic looks like a centrally located glistening, undivided, almost spotless white circle and surrounded by dark and narrow wrinkle free perimeter. The species differs from its known congeners by a combination of taxonomic features. In comparison with other described species, only three species, namely *Trichodina jadratica* Raabe, 1958, *T. australis* Su and White, 1995 and *T. mystusi* Asmat and Haldar, 1998, were found to resemble *Trichodina dakatiae* sp. n.

Trichodina jadratica was first described by Raabe (1958) from the gills of an Adriatic fish, *Barbatus mullatus*. Later, it has been reported worldwide from marine, brackish and freshwater animals. Xu (2007) revised and redescribed this species in details based on his personal study and published data. *T. jadratica* may seem similar to the current new species discussed in this paper but in close observation both the species differs to a great extent in their structure of the denticle and the central area of the adhesive disc (Figure 5B). In *T. jadratica*: the blade is broad, rectangular to a lesser extent (vs broad and smoothly curved); the blade extends beyond the y+1 axis (vs never extends the y+1 axis); the apex of blade is conical in shape (vs always rounded); the anterior margin of blade slopes down angularly (vs the anterior margin forms smooth curve); the depression of blade is distinct (vs not prominent); the anterior blade apophysis is always present (vs absent); the semilunar curve is '<-shaped (vs narrow and elongated); the tip of central part rarely extends halfway past of the y-1 axis (vs the tip always extends more than halfway, sometimes touches the y-1 axis); the central area of adhesive disc is large with argentophilic patches and wrinkled perimeter (vs small having no argentophilic patch or granule). Morphometric comparison between *T. jadratica* and the presently described species is given in Table 1.

Figures 3A-D. Photomicrograph of silver impregnated adhesive discs of *Trichodina dakatiae* sp. n. from the gills of *Mystus gulio* from Bangladesh.

Scale bar 20 μ m.

Figures 4A-B. Schematic drawing of denticles of *Trichodina dakatiae* sp. n. from the gills of *Mystus gulio* in Beel Dakatia, Khulna, Bangladesh.

Figures 5. Schematic drawings of the silver nitrate-impregnated denticles of *Trichodina dakatiae* sp. n. obtained in Bangladesh with other related trichodinid ciliates.

(A) *Trichodina dakatiae* sp. n., (B) *Trichodina jadranica* (after Raabe, 1958), (C) *Trichodina australis* (after Su and White, 1995), and *Trichodina mystusi* (after Asmat and Haldar, 1998).

Trichodina australis was first described by Su and White (1995) from the gills of *Atherinosoma microstoma* type-host, *Leptatherina presbyteroides*, *Kestratherina brevirostris*, *K. esox* and *K. hepsetoides* in south-eastern Tasmania, Australia. At first glance, *T. australis* looked very similar to the presently discussed new species (Figure 5C). The main differences concern the structure of the denticle and the central area of the adhesive disc. In *T. australis*: the blade of denticle is spatula-shaped (vs soup spoons-shaped); the gap between the tangent point and following denticle is small (vs large); the apex of blade is indistinct (vs prominent, forms smooth curve); the ray is almost straight and projected to the centre of adhesive disc (vs anteriorly directed and slightly curved in posterior direction); the tip of ray slightly crosses the y+1 axis (vs the tip of ray remains in between the axes); the ray base is thick (vs thin); the ray apophysis is ill developed (vs sometimes well developed); and medium in size (vs small).

Like all other trichodinids, *Trichodina mystusi* is also characterized by the morphology of the silver impregnated adhesive disc. *T. mystusi* is the first valid species of a trichodinid ciliate described from the Indian subcontinent. The species was described from the gill filaments of *M. gulio* from the Matla River of West Bengal in India. Later, Sharmin (2007), in an academic research project (unpublished) reported *T. mystusi* for the second time from the Master Bari Pond in Cox's Bazar district of Bangladesh from the same host (*M. gulio*) and location (gill filaments) as reported by Asmat and Haldar (1998). The presently discussed species also isolated from the same host and location, and also resembles *T.*

mystusi by having general appearance of the body dimensions, morphology of denticle components and the central clear area (Figure 5D). However, in close observation the described new species differs from *T. mystusi* in several aspects, such as, in *T. mystusi*: the blade is small, broad and angular (vs medium, smoothly curved); the distal margin is rounded with blunt tangent point situated at the same level of the distal margin (vs smoothly curved with the tangent point below of the distal margin); the apex is not prominent (vs prominent); the shape of central part is robust, tapering towards sharp rounded tip (vs wide triangular with gradually pointed tip); the tip of central part extends half to the y-1 axis (vs extends more than half to the y-1 axis); ray is well developed and slightly curved in the anterior direction (vs slightly curved posteriorly with same width throughout); the ray fills almost entire space between the y-axis (vs extends more than half to the y+1 axis in mature individuals); and the central area is valesqueze type/circle within a circle/ring within a ring type (vs the clear circle with a few dark minute dots at the centre). The morphometric data of *T. mystusi* is not significantly different from the presently discussed ciliate (Table 1).

T. dakatiae sp. n. shows a high prevalence only during winter. Ten out of 48 hosts of *M. gulio* had been found to be infested with this ciliate, mostly in the winter season, i. e., November to January. This result confirms the study of Hossain et al. (2008) who recorded *T. domerguei* and *T. reticulata* with the highest infection rate during winter season. Similar observations were also made by Asmat and Haldar (1998), Bhuiyan and Musa (2008) and Kibria et al. (2011). According to Hossain et al. (2008) the seasonal outbreak of diseases found in the winter season for particular species leads to a conclusion that a biological factor of the host as well as the water quality may play an important role in that period.

Type host: Long Whiskers Catfish, *Mystus gulio* (Hamilton, 1822) (Actinopterygii: Siluriformes: Bagridae).

Type locality: Beel Dakatia (Longitudes 89°20'E and 89°35'E and Latitudes 22°45'N and 23°00'N) at Fultala and Dumuria Upazila of Khulna District, Khulna Division, Bangladesh.

Type Location: Gills.

Prevalence: 15 of 48 examined (31.25% in *M. gulio*).

Infection: Low.

Etymology: Named after the place of collection, Beel Dakatia, of the type host fish, *Mystus gulio* (Hamilton, 1822).

Type specimens: Holotype (CUMZ-MG 1 prepared on 14/12/2009) of dry silver stained slide; and two Paratypes (CUMZ-MG 2 and CUMZ-MG 3 prepared on 14/12/2009) of silver stained slides are deposited in the Museum of the Department of Zoology, University of Chittagong, Chattogram 4331, Bangladesh.

Table 1. Morphometric comparison of *Trichodina dakatiae* sp. n. obtained in Bangladesh with other related trichodinid ciliates.

Species	<i>T. jadranica</i>	<i>T. australis</i>	<i>T. mystusi</i> (n=20)	<i>T. dakatiae</i> sp.n. (n=15)
Host	<i>Mullus barbatus</i>	<i>Atherinosoma microstoma</i>	<i>Mystus gulio</i>	<i>Mystus gulio</i>
Locality	Adriatic Sea	Australia	India	Bangladesh
Location	Gills	Gills	Gills	Gills
Reference	Raabe (1958)	Su and White (1995)	Asmat and Haldar (1998)	Present paper
Diameter of body	34-43	41.5-54.0 (45.2)	27.6-36.8 (30.9±2.7)	21.3-30.1 (27.0±2.8)
adhesive disc	28-38	32.0-44.0 (35.7)	21.4-30.6 (25.0±2.7)	20.4-24.3 (22.2±1.6)
denticulate ring	16-22	17.0-22.0 (20)	13.3-18.4 (15.2±1.8)	12.6-13.6 (12.9±0.5)
central area	-	6.5-7.0 (6.8)	5.1-9.2 (6.8±1.0)	4.9-5.8 (5.2±0.4)
width of border membrane	-	5.0-6.0 (5.2)	1.5-4.1 (2.9±0.5)	2.4-2.9 (2.8±0.2)
Number of denticles	22-25	20-24 (22)	20-24 (21.5±1.1)	18-21 (19.9±0.9)
radial pins/denticle	8	6-8	5-7 (5.3±0.8)	4-6 (4.9±0.6)
Span of denticle	-	-	-	6.8-7.8 (7.4±0.5)
Length of denticle	-	5.0-6.0 (5.3)	2.5-5.1 (3.8±0.7)	2.9-3.9 (3.6±0.5)
ray	2.5-3	5.0-6.0 (5.5)	2.1-3.6 (2.8±0.5)	1.9-3.9 (3.2±0.7)
blade	3-4	4.0-4.5 (4.4)	2.5-3.6 (3.1±0.2)	2.4-2.9 (2.8±0.2)
width of central part	-	1.0-1.5 (1.2)	1.0-3.0 (1.9±0.4)	1.0-1.9 (1.5±0.5)
		370-380 °	-	-

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